

Glue Sniffing Addiction behavior Among the Children in Urban City of Bangladesh

Sadika Sultana Chowdhury^{1,*}, and Prabal Barua^{2,‡}

¹Department of Sociology and Sustainable Development, Premier University, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

²Department of Knowledge Management for Development, Young Power in Social Action, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

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Abstract

The population of street children in Bangladesh, has been increasing in recent years, along with a rise in substance misuse among this demographic. Glue inhalation is a prevalent occurrence among street children in numerous underdeveloped nations, including Bangladesh. From the different study based evidence found that glue sniffing problem exposing the children to various health and social hazards, such as respiratory problems, brain damage, addiction, violence, and stigma in the country. The authors conducted the study to assess the socioeconomic factors that influence glue sniffing among street children in the commercial capital city of Bangladesh including the effects on their lives and well-being. This study utilized a self-administered, inquiry-based questionnaire, and a survey was completed by authorized, trained personnel. The study finds that glue sniffing is mainly driven by poverty, family breakdown, peer pressure, and lack of education and opportunities. The study also reveals that glue sniffing has negative impacts on the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of the children, as well as their social relationships and future prospects. The study recommends that effective interventions should address the root causes of glue sniffing and provide comprehensive support and rehabilitation for the affected children. The study also suggests that further research is needed to understand the dynamics and diversity of glue sniffing among street children in different contexts and settings. This study is anticipated to facilitate the implementation of systematic measures for the cessation of drug usage, thereby supporting long-term rehabilitation programs for these children and safeguarding each child's right to a secure and healthy existence.

Keywords: Glue sniffing, Children, Health and Social hazards, Drugs, Rehabilitation.

*Email: joyetaprotik@gmail.com

‡Email: prabalims@gmail.com (Corresponding author)

1. Introduction

The rights of children have emerged as a critical issue in the developing world, as outlined in the United Nations Charter on the Rights of the Child in 1990; street children in major global cities have garnered significant attention to enhance their quality of life and secure a better future. Children represent a beacon of hope, serve as catalysts for societal progress, and possess the potential to be foundational elements in global development; therefore, they should not be overlooked by parents or government, but rather nurtured within a healthy environment. Numerous children are observed working or residing on the streets of urban areas globally. Street children populations are marginalized primarily in urban areas, making it challenging to ascertain their precise numbers and the extent of their hardships. In their marginalized condition, they represent a genuinely “hidden” community that was omitted from the national census, educational, or health data, primarily because to the absence of a proper address. Some study explored that youngsters who begin consuming inhalants or other solvents early in life are more likely to consume other illicit drugs in the future. Consequently, inhalant abuse intervention programs appear significant from a community health standpoint. [1-3]

In the early 1960s, the consequences of inhaling chemicals and their effects on societal health and individual well-being became a significant concern for researchers and the government. Simultaneously, reports have emerged regarding the misuse of several volatile compounds, including paint thinners, nail polish remover, petrol and lighter fluids. The phrase “glue-sniffing” has broadly evolved to refer to various forms of solvent addiction through inhalation. Glue-sniffing is often engaged in by young children as a precursor to alcohol misuse, perhaps due to its low cost, easy accessibility, and rapid onset of effects. [4-6]

Street children represent a neglected and vulnerable demographic in numerous metropolitan centers globally; nevertheless, accurately estimating their population and the extent of their challenges proves difficult. Glue sniffing typically denotes volatile substance abuse (VSA), characterized by the deliberate inhalation of solvents to achieve psychoactive effects. These volatile solvents are found in several items, including paints, rubber, medicines, adhesives, and dendritic glues, rendering them readily accessible. The practice of glue sniffing is associated with multiple morbidities

affecting the respiratory, cardiac, and renal systems, as well as intoxication, increased risk of other addictions, and perhaps sudden sniffing death syndrome. Children's addiction to glue sniffing is a prevalent issue among street children in Thailand, Indonesia, Cambodia, Malaysia, Pakistan, Bangladesh, India, and the Philippines. [7, 8]

Glue sniffing is discovered as comprehensive preponderating as an inhalant use. In the USA approximately 20% of pubescent have speculated its application. The average age of initial inhalant abusers is discovered 13 years with the onslaught in children at 6 to 8 years. In addition, a repudiate in its use occurs at the age of 17 to 19 years. Nevertheless, some abusers persist in the addiction up to adulthood. Again, other felonious medicines are discovered as a forerunner of it in later years. [9, 10]

Many heroin addicts and IV drug abusers have a history of inhalant use, which is more common in those from a lower socioeconomic background, particularly those from chaotic, broken homes and abusive families. Other risk factors for inhalant abuse include those with aggressive behavior, low self-esteem, positive family history of abuse or alcoholism, peer pressure, poor academic achievement, abuse or neglect, and those who have been exposed to violence or assault. Heavy inhalant abusers, especially females, are more likely to have had a background of childhood physical or sexual abuse than non-abusers or lighter abusers. [11]

Inhalants or solvents are volatile substances at room temperature that induce effects akin to alcohol or anesthetics when their vapors are inhaled. Common members of this class of inhalants include toluene, petrol, kerosene, carbon tetrachloride, amyl nitrate, and specific anaesthetic agents such as halothane and nitrous oxide. Recent observations indicate that the misuse of these agents is escalating in certain nations. Typically, youngsters begin to experiment with inhalants around the age of twelve, but their usage diminishes significantly beyond the age of twenty-two. Individuals who persist in utilizing these substances cultivate a psycho-pathological condition and concomitant social issues. [12]

Many young individuals who use inhalants resort to alcohol and cannabis as they mature. Inhalants generate many effects, ranging from alcohol-like drunkenness to those akin to hallucinogens; this impact manifests swiftly and diminishes within minutes. Inhalants are found in everyday household items, including glue, paints, nail polish remover,

dry cleaning solvents, and degreasing agents. Others exist as propellant gases in aerosols and fire extinguishers, or as fuels such as petrol or lighter gas. Occasionally, individuals enhance the effects by amplifying the vapour concentration and minimizing air exposure, such as by inhaling through a plastic bag placed over their head, a perilous practice even in the absence of the chemical agent. Inhaled solvent vapors are absorbed by the lungs and swiftly attain the brain. A portion of the effect is attributable to diminished oxygen intake. Physiological functions such as respiration and cardiac rhythm are inhibited, and excessive or profound inhalation may lead to a "overdose," resulting in disorientation, loss of control, and coma. Under typical conditions, sniffers promptly recuperate.

The sensation closely resembles intoxication; adolescents engage in merriment and playful antics together. Experienced sniffers may pursue dream-like experiences; nonetheless, they are typically not genuine hallucinations, as young individuals do not conflate them with reality. The effects of solvent vapours manifest rapidly and dissipate within several minutes to half an hour upon cessation of inhalation. Accidental death or injury may occur when someone become "intoxicated" from inhalants, particularly in hazardous settings such as balconies or near bodies of water. Excessive sniffing to the point of unconsciousness poses a risk of mortality due to asphyxiation from vomit. If the inhalation method for the solvent impedes respiration (such as using large plastic bags over the head or sniffing in enclosed areas) and the individual loses consciousness, asphyxia may result in death. Certain materials, particularly aerosol gases and cleaning fluids, might sensitive the heart and potentially lead to heart failure, especially if individuals engage in physical exertion simultaneously. Gases injected directly into the oral cavity can result in fatal asphyxiation. Fatalities are infrequent and largely preventable, despite the inability to eliminate sniffing itself. Inhaling glue from small bags placed against the mouth and nose has resulted in a minimal number of fatalities. Aerosol or butane gas inhalation, as well as the use of sacks placed over the head, have been comparatively more associated, although being less widespread activities. [13-15]

Very long-term heavy solvent misuse over ten years-might results in moderate but lasting impairment of brain function, affecting especially the control of movement. Chronic misuse of

aerosols and cleaning fluids has caused lasting kidney and liver damage, whilst repeatedly sniffing leaded petrol may result in lead poisoning. Despite these possibilities, it seems that lasting damage attributable to solvent misuse is extremely rare. Whilst someone is sniffing repeatedly, the "hangover" effects of pallor, fatigue, forgetfulness and loss of concentration tend to become a recurring daily pattern. The youngster's performance and functioning are affected and there can be weight loss, depression and tremors. But these will clear up once sniffing is discontinued. Tolerance develops, but physical dependence is not a significant problem. Psychological dependence develops in a minority of susceptible youngsters with underlying family or personality problems, and these will probably become "lone sniffers," as opposed to the more common pattern of sniffing in groups [16, 17]. The use of inhalants, including glue sniffing, is extensively common. Reports indicate that approximately 20% of adolescents in the USA have engaged in its use. The average age of initial inhalant misuse is 13 years, with onset observed in youngsters as young as 6 to 8 years old. Usage diminishes between the ages of 17 and 19, however certain abusers persist throughout adulthood. Furthermore, it serves as a forerunner to the consumption of other illicit substances in subsequent years. A significant number of heroin addicts and intravenous drug users have a history of inhalant use, which is more prevalent among individuals from poorer socioeconomic backgrounds, especially those from tumultuous, dysfunctional households and abusive environments. Additional risk factors for inhalant abuse encompass individuals exhibiting aggressive behaviour, possessing low self-esteem, having a familial history of abuse or alcoholism, experiencing peer pressure, demonstrating poor academic performance, undergoing abuse or neglect, and those exposed to violence or assault. Female heavy inhalant abusers are more likely to have experienced childhood abuse, either physical or sexual, compared to non-abusers or those who abuse inhalants lightly [18, 19]. The inaugural case of glue sniffing in Singapore was documented in 1977 involving a 15-year-old American male, discovered deceased in his room with aeroplane glue, an adhesive utilized for assembling scale model kits, lodged in his nostrils. He exhibited elevated toluene levels in the bloodstream. Since then, there has been a rise in glue sniffing, peaking in 1987 when 1,112 abusers were penalized. A decrease in glue-sniffing prevalence was observed

in the subsequent decade; however, it is regrettably experiencing a concerning resurgence. Data from the Central Narcotics Bureau, as reported in the Straits Times in April 2008, indicated that the number of inhalant abusers apprehended in 2007 was 644, an increase from 403 in 2006 and 120 in 2020. Among the 644 abusers, 70% were individuals under the age of 20, and 80% were male.

The predominant factors cited for the abuse were peer pressure, ennui, and curiosity. Glue sniffing constitutes a criminal offence in Singapore, necessitating the initiation of a police case. Inhalant abusers might be categorized as experimenters, infrequent users, or chronic abusers [20, 21].

Figure 1: Geographical location of the Study Area.

Source: “Bangladesh”. *Wikipedia*. Wikipedia.org CC BY-SA 4.0. (2024).

The purpose of examining glue-sniffing youngsters in Chittagong Metropolitan City is to comprehend the socioeconomic elements, familial dynamics, and environmental influences that contribute to this troubling behaviour. Examining the prevalence and root causes can guide focused actions, enhancing the welfare of these children and contributing to overall community health. [20, 21]

Youngsters represent the future of Bangladesh, where there is a rising population of street

youngsters, many of whom engage in different criminal activities. In addition to glue sniffing, various other illegal activities are taking place. The incidence of children participating in illicit activities such as glue sniffing is increasing daily in the Chittagong Metropolitan area. Propose a multifaceted issue necessitating comprehensive analysis and intervention. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of glue sniffing among children in Chittagong Metropolitan City by addressing these aspects, hence offering significant insights for intervention and prevention efforts. The

authors undertook the study to investigate the social elements linked to glue sniffing, evaluate the socioeconomic status of adolescents acquainted with glue sniffing, and examine the effects of glue sniffing on the young population in the study area [20, 21].

2. Materials and Methods

Chittagong serves as the primary seaport of the nation, divisional headquarters, and a significant hub for trade, commerce, and industry. The port city of Chittagong consistently ranked as the second urban centre over the entire period. It manages the predominant volume of the nation's exports and imports. The estimated population is approximately 4 million, with males constituting 54.36% and females 45.64%. The population density is 15,276 per square kilometre. Chittagong, the second-largest city in Bangladesh, is marked by a multifaceted socioeconomic environment. Multiple circumstances render it a significant area of inquiry about glue-sniffing youngsters, since Chittagong has seen fast urbanization, resulting in heightened migration and a greater concentration of at-risk populations, including street children. Bangladesh exhibits a moderate level of urbanization; yet, the urban population growth rate is significantly high, resulting in a substantial absolute population due to the big total population. 'Aparajay Bangladesh' reports that the present population of street children in the Chittagong division is 55,000, with around 2,000 located at the Chittagong Railway Station, Kotwali, Riaz Uddin Bazar, Sholshahar, Kadmatoli, New Bridge, Patenga, Agrabad, and Halishahar areas [22]. As a port and commercial metropolis, street youngsters are readily susceptible to drug involvement (Figure 1).

The authors utilised both primary and secondary data, with primary data gathered via a questionnaire administered through face-to-face interviews. The majority of the questionnaire consisted of structured questions, supplemented by a limited number of semi-structured enquiries. The necessary data have been obtained from secondary sources, including books, reports, journal articles, publications, newspapers, and online resources. The study utilized primary data acquired from judgmentally sampled glue-sniffing children in Chittagong Metropolitan City. The study was executed from January 2024 to March 2024. The current investigation was conducted using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was initially

pretested and subsequently revised. The stratified random sampling method was employed to pick the respondents. The sample size was determined using a statistically representative formula (Islam, 2014), such as equation:

$$n_0 = \left(\frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where n_0 = desire sample size, z = standard normal deviate usually set at 1.96, which corresponds to the 95% confidence level ($z = 1.96$), p = assumes proportion in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic ($p = 0.5$), q = proportion of the estimation of population ($q = 1-p$), d = allowable maximum error in estimating a population proportion ($d = 0.05$).

Moreover, Simple Random sampling technique was adopted for successfully operating of 91 questionnaires at a household's level of the displaced people. Considering the representative sample size, the authors have distributed those samples on the statistical way with the help of following equation:

$$\text{Random sampling, } N_j = \left(\frac{n}{N} \right) N_i \quad (2)$$

where, N_j = represents the sample size, N = total population size, ($N = n_i + n_{ii} + n_{iii} + \dots + n_n$), N_i = population size of study area, n = desired sample size.

The study employs a descriptive and qualitative methodology. A total of 50 children engaged in glue sniffing have been identified by judgemental sampling. The study area is confined only to Chittagong Metropolitan City. In-depth interviews were conducted via a judgemental sampling strategy. Fifty interviews were performed in person. A semi-structured questionnaire was created to gather information from children engaged in glue sniffing. To enhance precision and ensure data efficiency and impartiality, it is essential to employ a statistical sampling rate during data gathering. A probability sampling technique, specifically random sampling, is employed based on the field situation during the interview. Sampling is most effective in scenarios when a limited number of individuals in a group possess the characteristics anticipated by the researcher for the target population. The data processing encompasses editing, coding, tabulating, and analyzing the data with MS Excel and SPSS. Upon concluding the fieldwork, the compiled data underwent meticulous editing, which involved

validating and rectifying any inaccuracies to identify potential discrepancies and inconsistencies. Editing must fulfil three criteria: thoroughness, accuracy, and uniformity. Editing was conducted to ascertain the accuracy of the acquired material, ensuring that the appropriate sample was interviewed and that three specific questions from the questionnaire were posed by me on the day of the interview.

3. Results and Discussions

The authors interviewed 50 glue sniffers, of whom about 60% were male and 20% were female. Among the interviewed youth, the authors discovered that 36% of the respondents are aged 11-14 years, 30% are over 14 years, 12% are under 5-8 years, 12% are aged 8-11 years, and 10% are under 5 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Sample Distribution According to the Respondents Age.

Age (year)	Frequency	%
11-14	18	36
8-11	6	12
5-8	6	12
Above 14	15	30
Under 5	5	10
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

The authors found that 56% of the total respondents residing in slum areas were followed by those living in parks, streets, and public places (Table 2).

Table 2. Percentage of the Respondents Residence Status.

	Frequency	%
Park/Street	13	26
Public place	7	14
Slum	28	56
Work place	2	4
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

According to Figure 2, the authors discovered that 86% of the respondents lack any prior schooling.

Fourteen percent possess primary education (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage of respondents' education.

Source: Authors.

The authors discovered that among the surveyed street youths, 18% engage in rag picking, 16% participate in everyday labour, and 72% are presently unemployed (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percentage of respondents' job type.

Source: Authors.

In the poll, the authors found that 58% of respondents lack familial connections, 10% are part of a nuclear family, and 16% come from a single-parent household. 12% belong to a relative home, while 4% belong to an extended family (Table 3).

Table 3: Family Status of the interviewed Street Children.

Family Type	Frequency	%
Single	29	58
Extended	2	4
Nuclear	5	10
Relative household	6	12
Single Parent	8	16
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

In the study, the author discovered that 34% of total drug users smoke cannabis, 14% use yaba, 2% consume alcohol, 2% use opium, 3% are addicted to sleeping medications, and 42% exclusively use dandy among the 50 interviewed street children. According to Figure 3, the authors found that 30% of respondents have been glue-sniffing for 4-8 months, 22% for 1-2 years, 10% for less than 4 months, 16% for 8-12 months, and 22% for more than 2 years (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Duration of the habituated of Glue Shifting.

Source: Authors.

The survey revealed that 8% of respondents initiated glue-sniffing through experimentation, 24% out of curiosity, 6% for thrill-seeking, 16% due to peer pressure, and 56% as a result of despair (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Percentage of reasons behind first-time inhalation.

Source: Authors.

According to Figure 6, the survey revealed that 36% of glue shifters utilized it four times daily, 16% inhaled it three times daily, 28% inhaled it twice daily, 12% drank it once daily, and 8% inhaled it more than four times daily (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Percentage of inhaling count (per day).

Source: Authors.

The authors determined that 40% of respondents purchase dandy from a dealer, 38% from a peer, 18% from motor garages, and 4% from a hardware store in Chittagong City. The study revealed that 18% of respondents support their drug use through rag picking, 46% resort to begging, 8% borrow

from relatives, and 28% declined to answer this question (Table 4). In the poll, the scientists discovered that 32% of glue shifters recognized the detrimental repercussions of substance addiction, whereas 68% remained unaware of these adverse consequences (Figure 6).

Table 4: Source of Finance for Drug Purchase.

DRUG FINANCE		
Valid	Frequency	%
Begging	23	46
Borrowing from family	4	8
Rag picking	9	18
Salary oriented job	0	0
Not interested to say	14	28
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

Figure 6. Percentage of realization of bad effects of drug addiction.

Source: Authors.

4. Discussions

The majority of street youngsters in Dhaka and Chittagong engage in labour within the Tokai district, where they gather dandies from inexpensive hardware stores. Advocate Saimul Islam Rabi, an executive member of a civil rights organization, asserts that street children, being inherently vulnerable and devoid of social rights, readily engage in criminal activities. Their susceptibility to drug addiction exacerbates their desperation, resulting in theft and robbery. Street youngsters in Chittagong, Bangladesh, are participating in a perilous drug addiction referred to as Dandy Banaya Khai. The primary component for producing Dandy is a specifically formulated Ika gum utilized in the shoe making industry. Children aged 11 to 15 are under the influence of drugs and engage in criminal activities such as stealing and

robbery to obtain funds. Suman Mandal Chatter, Deputy Director of the Narcotics Control Directorate in Chittagong Metro, declared that the Narcotics Control and Amendment Act designates all individuals under 18 as children. A correctional facility for mothers with substance use disorders and their children could assist in rehabilitating a limited number of street children, reintegrating them into society. 'Aparajay Bangladesh' reports that the present population of street children in the Chittagong division is 55,000, with around 2,000 located in the areas of Chittagong Railway Station, Kotwali, Riaz Uddin Bazar, Sholshahar, Kadmatoli, New Bridge, Patenga, Agrabad, and Halishahar. The organisation is enhancing its "Child to Child contract" initiative to safeguard street children from substance addiction and has sought a meeting with law enforcement to implement actions against drug traffickers exploiting street children.

The scientists identified a significant association between youngsters who engage in glue sniffing and those originating from dysfunctional family environments. A significant proportion of these children indicated that they endured various types of abuse from their stepmothers or stepfathers, leading them to seek shelter on the streets. A substantial number resorted to substance misuse, including drug usage and inhalant consumption, to manage their traumatic background. The literacy rate among children who sniff glue was exceedingly low. Approximately 86% were illiterate or without formal schooling. Merely 14% own primary education, and no individuals were identified with secondary school education. Despite the prolonged efforts of both Government and Non-Government Organizations to implement various programs aimed at providing primary education to impoverished and vulnerable children in urban areas, the sampled street children remain disadvantaged and overlooked due to inadequacies, substandard management, and the ineffectiveness of dropout interventions in reintegrating them from street life. Consequently, these youngsters have already created a challenge for the government to enhance the national schooling rate.

The authors found that 56% of the respondents reside in slum areas, 26% in parks or streets, 4% at their workplaces, and 14% in public spaces. Consequently, they have encountered numerous issues. Numerous individuals had been afflicted by various health issues stemming from contaminated drinking water, unsanitary food consumption, soiled clothing, and inadequate sanitation due to their

transient lifestyles. During the interview, the majority of our respondents indicated that they suffer from numerous ailments, including dermatological conditions and sexually transmitted infections. This study illuminated the detrimental impacts of glue-sniffing on children's physical and emotional well-being. Prolonged exposure to glue inhalation has been associated with respiratory diseases, cognitive deterioration, and behavioral issues. This underscores the essential necessity for intervention and support services to address children's health challenges.

Excessive consumption of dandelion can adversely affect essential organs, including the kidneys, liver, lungs, and neurological system. Table 3 indicates that, beside malnutrition, street children also consume various substances including opium, yaba, alcohol, sleeping medications, and cannabis, hence elevating their risk of mortality. Children who are frequently exposed to glue often develop a dependency and addiction to it. Deprivation of glue may result in anxiety and violent behaviour. Table No. 6 demonstrates that adolescents who excessively consume candy often do so more than two to four times daily.

Marginalized communities appear to be disproportionately impacted by excessive dandy use. Poverty constitutes a significant socioeconomic challenge. Table 4 illustrates that most contemporary research indicate that most street children originate from dysfunctional families that have faced considerable economic and familial challenges in the past. The table further illustrates the increased incidence of these difficulties among children reared by single parents, divorced husbands, and divorced wives.

Adolescents are more inclined to consume junk due to its accessibility and low cost; yet, this behaviour adversely affects their physical and emotional well-being. Table No. 5 indicates that street youths have been observed to ingest dandy out of curiosity owing to its readily available nature. Furthermore, adolescents cultivate a drug dependency on Dandy due to factors such as melancholy, isolation, thrill-seeking, or experimentation. Children residing on the streets and engaging in glue sniffing face numerous obstacles in educational settings, including elevated absenteeism and diminished performance across various courses. Table No. 4.4 indicates that 14% of children utilizing Dandy have attained only basic education, while around 86% of the youth are illiterate.

Dandy addicts finance their substance use through a variety of immoral and disorderly behaviors. Furthermore, young children are utilized in the drug trade. Approximately 20 percent of street youth engage in drug trafficking, as indicated in Table 4. The analysis of Table No. 4 reveals that approximately 46% of adolescents choose to solicit for discretionary funds.

Excessive consumption of dandy might adversely affect one's physical and emotional health. The effects of age differ for children and teenagers. Children experience physical constraints as they mature. Table 5 of the survey reveals that around 15% of adolescent street children are associated with drug use. Adolescent glue sniffing can lead to learning deficits, memory impairment, addiction, and social and academic difficulties, as well as diminished cognitive functions. Prompt intervention is crucial to prevent enduring consequences.

Inhaling glue fumes can be quite hazardous. Inhaling volatile chemicals, such as those found in adhesives, might result in asphyxiation or sudden cardiac arrest. Moreover, prolonged use may adversely affect the liver, heart, brain, and other vital organs. Decreased judgement and coordination elevate the probability of accidents and injuries. It is imperative to comprehend the gravity of these dangers and to respond promptly to aid those engaged in glue sniffing or other inhalant consumption. Table number. Table 6 indicates that only 32% of persons recognize the adverse effects of excessive dandelion use. The majority of adolescents who utilize Dandy perish prematurely due to the apathy of the remaining 68% of adults.

6. Recommendation

The authors advised using the following procedures to safeguard adolescents from drug habituation:

- Encourage parental engagement in children's life to cultivate a loving and nurturing atmosphere.
- Establish community centres that offer at-risk youth a safe environment. To deter children from engaging in hazardous behaviors, these facilities may incorporate mentor-ship programs, recreational activities, and vocational training.
- Collaborate with law enforcement to tackle the distribution and accessibility of glue products.

Enhance regulations and monitor the distribution of substances commonly misused by adolescents. This addresses the enforcement of age restrictions and penalties for violation.

- Implement supportive counselling programs in educational institutions and communities to provide emotional and psychological assistance to youngsters affected by glue-sniffing. Engage skilled specialists capable of addressing the underlying causes of this behaviour.

7. Conclusions

This study has examined the intricate dimensions of glue sniffing and demonstrated its diverse impacts. The practice perpetuates the cycle of substance abuse and endangers communal well-being. Glue sniffers often experience psychological issues, underscoring the need for targeted interventions. Moreover, the recognized health ramifications underscore the urgent necessity for the implementation of comprehensive preventative programs. To effectively intervene and enhance society, it is essential to regard glue sniffing as a multifaceted issue encompassing societal, psychological, health, and behaviour components.

The ecological consequences of glue inhalation predominantly stem from the inadequate disposal of adhesive containers and associated components. This results in littering, hazardous substances, waste management issues, urban deterioration, and public safety risks. Abandoned adhesive containers exacerbate litter, degrade soil and water quality, and provide safety hazards. Effective garbage disposal methods and community education are essential to alleviate these adverse effects. Tackling substance misuse and advocating for appropriate waste disposal methods can alleviate the adverse effects of glue sniffing.

The public health risk of glue sniffing encompasses heightened healthcare demands, mental health challenges, community safety issues, disease transmission, educational interruptions, societal pressures, financial repercussions, and stigma. It impacts healthcare resources, mental health, education, social services, law enforcement, and community support networks. The enduring health ramifications and stigma may result in elevated healthcare expenses and economic strain. Resolving this necessitates a holistic strategy, encompassing

education, preventive initiatives, accessible treatment options, and community assistance.

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